

Why is Quantum Mechanics Sometimes Formulated in Terms of Fisher Information?

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In (1) the Schrodinger equation is derived using the extremization of Fisher information in a certain way formulated in (2) i.e. Extreme Physical Information. Fisher information, however, is defined in terms of $P(x)$ which in quantum mechanics is $W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction. As a result, the Schrodinger equation is derived in terms of $P(x)$ and then the mathematical substitution $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state “simplifies” the form of the equation. Otherwise there would be no need to introduce the wavefunction. Furthermore $P(x) = \text{constant}$ for a quantum free particle which is also a solution of the Schrodinger equation. For $P(x)=\text{constant}$, however, one would normally not consider using the Fisher information.

We further note that in a physical example, namely that of the reflection/refraction of light from an interface of media one is forced to introduce the concept of a wavefunction i.e. the square root of flux, otherwise the problem cannot be solved. Thus in this situation one does not solve the problem in terms of $P(x)$ and then introduce $W(x)$ to simplify the form. In particular, if one considers a single photon moving to the right, it either reflects or refracts (with probability), but the ensuing equations involve the weight of the square root fluxes (wavefunctions) of all three. How can this be unless there is uncertainty in time and space which allows one to have all three together? Thus the reflection/refraction problem depends on square root probability or flux and introduces the idea of uncertainty in x, t . Given the translational invariance in the problem, it is natural to introduce the translation operator d/dx . In fact, one may define the uncertainty in x such that one has an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$ i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. This is complex and so its modulus respects $P(x)=\text{constant}$ which would yield a Fisher’s information of 0, meaning that there is no probability and hence no need for Fisher’s information. There is, however, probability in x , but a different level than the deterministic $x=vt$ where $v=\text{constant}$.

Thus we argue that one may obtain $\exp(ipx)$ strictly from the notion of translational invariance. In other words, Fisher information is not required to find this form and the quantum physics associated with it. Nevertheless Fisher information and EPI (Extreme physical Information) may be used to derive the Schrodinger equation (applied to a bound state) and one may deduce $\exp(ipx)$ from this. We note, however, that Fisher information makes use of d/dx which is the translational generator and so the idea of translational invariance and Fisher’s information/EPI may be linked.

Fisher’s Information

Fisher’s information is formally part of statistics. It deals with a probability distribution and its first derivative with respect to an “unknown deterministic parameter” (3) which one tries to determine from measurements. The definition of Fisher’s information from (1) is:

$$I = \int dy f(y,x) \left\{ \frac{1}{f} \frac{df}{dx} \right\} \left\{ \frac{1}{f} \frac{df}{dx} \right\} \quad ((1))$$

In (3), I is multiplied by n, the number of data samples taken. In (1) it is noted that one may consider problems for which $f(y,x) = f(y-x)$ and then the Fisher information becomes:

$$\text{Integral } dx \frac{1}{f} \frac{df}{dx} \frac{df}{dx} \quad ((2))$$

An important property of I (called the Cramer-Rao bound) is that:

$$\text{Variance}(x) \geq 1/I \quad ((3))$$

In (2), however, a principle of extreme information (EPI) is developed. It is argued that $I=J$ (where J is linked to some given or measured information such as a potential $V(x)$ etc) represents an extreme physical information situation which is said to prevail in much of physics. In particular, this principle is said to account for the Lagrangian formalism and the Schrodinger equation as examples.

Principle of Extreme Physical Information (EPI)

We consider the (EPI) approach to finding the Schrodinger equation as developed in (1). We wish to point out that I utilizes only $f(x)$ the probability distribution, so the notion of a wavefunction does not appear a priori. This means one need not consider a wavefunction for the Schrodinger equation at all (applied to a bound state), It could be written in terms of density (where $\text{density}=f(x)=W(x)W(x)$ with $W(x)=\text{the bound state wavefunction}$). The wavefunction is only introduced to simplify the form of the Fisher information written in terms of $f(x)$. We have an issue with this that will be presented in the next section, but first we present the derivation of the Schrodinger equation using EPI as given in (1).

It is first assumed that a set of average values of quantities $A_i(x)$ i.e. $\text{Integral } A_i(x)f(x)dx$ are known with $i=1$ to m . (Note: $A_i(x)$ could be the classical potential $V(x)$.)

Then one extremizes:

$$\Delta \{ I - b \text{Integral } dx f(x) - \text{Sum over } i \ C_i \text{Integral } A_i(x)f(x)dx \} = 0 \quad ((4))$$

(Note: b and C_i are Lagrange multipliers and $\text{Integral } f(x)dx = 1$ is a constraint which is part of the extremization.) Then:

$$\{ 1/ff \frac{df}{dx} \frac{df}{dx} + d/dx (2/f \frac{df}{dx}) \} + b + \text{Sum over } i \ C_i A_i(x) = 0 \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is essentially the Schrodinger equation expressed in terms of $f(x)=\text{Probability}(x)$. If one introduces $P(x)=f(x) = W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is a math function, :

$$-5 \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) - \text{Sum over } i \ C_i/8 A_i(x)W(x) = b/8 W(x) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) is the familiar form of the Schrodinger equation. (The above derivation follows directly from (1)).

An immediate issue that we have is that the Schrodinger equation for no potential is of the form:

$$-\frac{5}{2} \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} = E W \quad ((7))$$

$\exp(ipx)$ is a solution for a free quantum particle wavefunction, but it is also a solution of ((7)). The problem is that $P(x)=f(x) = W^*(x)W(x) = 1$ (or $1/\sqrt{L}$ to be normalized over a length L). $P(x)=1/L$ is a constant and so one would not use Fisher's information in such a case, but a free particle is a reality. It seems that to use the approach of (1), one must consider a bound scenario for which one has $\exp(ipx) \pm \exp(-ipx)$ terms e.g. $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$. This, however, suggests that there is something peculiar about a free particle, namely that both p and $-p$ have a real symmetric (even) piece $\cos(px)$ to which a second distribution $\sin(px)$ is added in a second dimension. Thus we try to argue that there may be an alternative way of finding $\exp(ipx)$ than Fisher's information or EPI. We do note, however, that using EPI for a bound quantum state, does allow one to deduce $\exp(ipx)$. We consider this in more detail in the next section.

One Dimensional Reflection/Refraction of Light

Consider the one dimensional reflection/refraction of light upon changing from a medium with n =index of refraction=1 to n_2 at $x=0$. This problem may be considered in terms of a single photon, but also by a steady state picture with many photons.

We argue that one MUST use the notion of wavefunction or square root of flux to solve it. One cannot simply use probability density as in the Fisher information case (and introduce $P(x)=f(x)=W(x)W(x)$ for simplification reasons.)

In particular, an energy conservation equation based on flux/intensity = number of photons * $E \cdot c = AA$ (to show positivity) where E is the same for the incident/reflected and refracted photons is:

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c^2 \quad ((8))$$

This is one equation with two unknowns B, C (in terms of a given A) and so it cannot be solved. Furthermore it applies to a steady stream picture. In the case of a single photon E is the same for all cases, so one does not need to write an equation in the form of ((8)) unless it is linked to probabilities. That seems to be a key to solving ((8)). ((8)) is written in terms of a time grouping i.e. the incident beam on the LHS and the reflected and refracted on the left. If one moves BB/c to the LHS, one has a grouping by space (with time gone and hence determinism gone i.e $x=ct$ gone) as well as a difference of square which leads to two equations (using $E=pc$):

$$A+B = C \quad ((9a)) \quad \text{and} \quad pA-pB = p^2C \quad ((9b))$$

((9a)) and ((9b)) may be solved for B, C in terms of A . Thus one must rely on the square root flux or wavefunction. A second issue arises. Why should A, B, C appear in the same equation? For

$n_2 > n_1 = 1$, $B < 0$ so $A+B$ dampens A for $A > 0$ and $A > C > 0$. A , however, should not exist at the same time as B or C if one has a single photon. There would either be reflection or refraction. Thus we suggest (as we have done before) that there is uncertainty of space in the problem. Time is removed because one started with a steady state picture. Thus a free moving photon which follows $x=ct$ only does so on average. There must be a small x -distribution included and this must repeat according to space invariance.

Thus the key idea becomes spatial invariance. The generator of translation is d/dx and the free particle action is $-Et+px$ (relativistic or nonrelativistic where $x/t=v$), so we consider eigenfunctions:

$$-i\hbar d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((10))$$

((10)) is not the same as the Schrodinger kinetic energy term which follows from Fisher information. It is an eigenfunction of the translation operator and yields a complex probability which is required to solve the reflection/refraction problem.

For a particle in a potential, however, two probabilistic considerations occur because one forms an average of $\exp(ipx)$ s which are already probabilistic and then needs to find weights so there is a probability to have each p value i.e.

$$W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((11))$$

Fisher Information Extremization and Classical Conservation of Energy

Given ((11)) one may consider Newtonian conservation of energy: $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ and write an average kinetic energy using:

$$\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((12)) \text{ or}$$

$$-1/2m \ d^2W/dx^2 / W + V(x) = E_n \quad ((13))$$

Given the differential equation ((13)) and its boundary conditions, only a discrete set of E_n 's are allowed, not all energies.

There are EPI arguments (5) that $KE(x) + V(x) = E$ follows from extremization of Fisher information in classical physics.

Even if that is the case, the notion of $\exp(ipx)$, which does not need to follow from Fisher information, but from spatial invariance, dictates the form of the average $KE(x) = \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ exp(ipx)\} / W(x)$. This function in general will have peaks and troughs just like $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$, but with different heights and widths. Thus it is the form $\exp(ipx)$ which has a large bearing on the quantum bound state result and this result follows directly from the translational generator d/dx .

Thus Fisher information/EPI may govern the form of a conservation of energy equation. From this one may deduce the form of a free particle i.e. $\cos(px)+i \sin(px)$. Alternatively, one does not need to use conservation of energy equation (Schrodinger equation) and hence one does not need to utilize EPI/Fisher's information to obtain $\exp(ipx)$. It follows as the eigenfunction of the translation operator. One may note that Fisher's information makes use of the translation operator d/dx and so that may be the connection between the two approaches, EPI and finding $\exp(ipx)$ using translational invariance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that one may use EPI (Fisher's information) to derive the form of the Schrodinger equation as done in (1). We note, however, that this derivation applies to a bound system and a priori only makes use of $W(x)$ where $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ to simplify the form of a differential equation.

If one examines a free particle case, however, $P(x)=1/L$ (for a length L) because all x points have the same probability. Thus one would not use Fisher's information in the first place, but a free quantum particle is also a solution of the Schrodinger equation (for $V(x)=0$). Thus we suggest that the form $\exp(ipx)$ has its own origins which do not depend on energy and hence on Fisher's information.

In particular, we present the example of reflection/refraction in one dimension at an interface of media at $x=0$. One may write a steady state flux equation $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c$ where A,B,C refer to the incident, reflected and refracted beams and AA is used to show positivity. The problem is that one cannot solve for two unknowns (in terms of A) with one equation. If one brings BB/c to the LHS one may obtain two equations using a difference of squares, but this means the essential consideration is the square root probability or flux.

At this level, one should be able to describe a single photon, but in principle it should not be linked to both the reflected and refracted photons. Furthermore, the reflected photon is on the LHS side as if it existed at the same time as the incident one. This suggests, uncertainty in position as time has been removed (due to the steady state nature of the problem).

This uncertainty in space, however, must be linked to spatial invariance because a single beam moves through space as if each x point had the same weight. A solution is to take the eigenfunction of the translation operator $-id/dx$ to find $\exp(ipx)$.

$\exp(ipx)$ does happen to be a solution of the Schrodinger equation which may be derived using EPI i.e. Fisher's information, but one may find it simply by using the translation operator. This introduces the idea of a wavelength \hbar/p , but also the notion of $\exp(ipx)$ having a modulus of 1 so all x points have the same weight.

Thus it seems that one may use EPI and obtain the Schrodinger equation for a bound state and then deduce the form $\exp(ipx)$. Alternatively, one may find $\exp(ipx)$ using translational invariance (it is an eigenfunction of $-id/dx$). The two approaches are be linked, at least superficially, by the fact that Fisher's information also uses the translational generator.

References

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